

FORENSIC REGISTRATION AND IDENTIFICATION OF PERSONS IN THE REPUBLIC OF NORTH MACEDONIA

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Abstract

This paper focuses on the procedures for forensic registration and identification of persons and the forensic methods applied in these processes in the Republic of North Macedonia.

Criminalistic registration is examined through the practical work of the organizational units of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, with a particular emphasis on the introduction of the new ABIS system.

Identification, on the other hand, is analysed as a forensic identification process carried out through personal description, papillary lines, and DNA identification. The chapters of the paper pay special attention to the provisions arising from the introduction of the new Guidelines for forensic registration and identification of persons and unknown remains.

The aim of the paper is to identify the challenges encountered in practice during the implementation of the aforementioned processes and to propose solutions for overcoming them. Ultimately, establishing the identity of a potential perpetrator is, in our view, the most critical aspect of forensic work.

Keywords: *forensics, registration, identification*

INTRODUCTION

The registration and identification of persons form the basis of forensic work. Establishing the identity of an individual's distinguishing characteristics (suspect, perpetrator, or victim) or an object in an investigation is a critical step without which the successful completion of the forensic work is impossible. The focus of this paper will be exclusively on the registration and identification of persons.

We consider it useful to first distinguish between the concepts of registration and identification, specifically in a forensic context. The term forensic registration, as defined in our legislation, specifically in the Guidelines on Conducting Forensic Registration and Identification of Persons and Unknown Remains (hereinafter: the Guidelines), in Article 2 is described as follows: "a procedure for obtaining identification markers (characteristics – legal, factual, and physical) for a person or remains, with the aim of their identification" (Guidelines on Conducting Forensic Registration and Identification of Persons and Unknown Remains, 2024).

Regarding the term forensic identification, many authors in the literature provide similar definitions. According to professor Vodinelić, the identification of persons entails: "determining all characteristics by which one person is distinguished from all others. These include: characteristics of a legal nature (name, surname); factual nature (date of birth,

place of birth, etc.); and physical characteristics (the personal appearance of the individual with their distinguishing features)” (Vodinelić, 1978).

In brief, registration involves the procedure of collecting/securing data about an individual, while identification involves the procedure of verifying/confirming the accuracy of that data.

We believe it is important to outline the legal bases under which law enforcement agencies (the police) undertake these actions. Specifically, the police are legally obligated to take measures and activities aimed at identifying the perpetrator of a criminal offense. Logically, to achieve this, it is necessary to know or establish their identity. To this end, the Criminal Procedure Law in Article 227 provides the following possibilities for the police: “When it is necessary for the purpose of establishing the identity of persons or objects, or in other cases relevant to successfully conducting the procedure, the judicial police may photograph the suspect, take fingerprints and palm prints, collect biological material for DNA analysis, and, with prior approval of the Public Prosecutor, publish their photograph. The judicial police may also collect samples from the suspect for DNA analysis”. (**Criminal Procedure Code** (2010) *Official Gazette of the Republic of Macedonia*, No. 150/2010)

The identification of the perpetrator of a criminal act is also mentioned as a concept in the Law on the Police. It is perhaps no coincidence that the first listed police jurisdiction in the Law is the verification and establishment of the identity of persons and objects. Regarding the establishment of identity, the Law in Article 40 states: “The identity of a person is established using methods and tools of criminalistic tactics and techniques, medical, or other appropriate expert examinations” (**Law on the Police**. (2006). *Official Gazette of the Republic of Macedonia*, No. 114/2006).

When it comes to the “methods and tools of criminalistic techniques,” these procedures primarily involve the methods and tools used by forensics, such as anthropometry (Bertillonage), dactyloscopy, mugshot photography, personal description, handwriting analysis, etc.

The development of science and the discovery of new possibilities for human identification have led to some of the aforementioned methods and tools being phased out of practice (e.g., Bertillonage). On the other hand, the discovery of the immense identification potential contained within the DNA molecule has opened new possibilities in forensic work, which in turn has led to the mandatory collection of biological material for DNA analysis.

In our country, the establishment of DNA databases began in 2011, and since that time, the collection of biological material has become a mandatory part of the registration of persons.

At the time of writing this paper, a transformation is underway regarding the method of fingerprint collection, specifically with the planned introduction of the new ABIS (Automated Biometric Identification System). Fingerprints are still collected using the traditional ink method, but in the upcoming period, the process is expected to be digitized through the use of LiveScan technology. The introduction of the ABIS system also includes changes to mugshot photography, which will be discussed in more detail in the following chapters.

1. CRIMINALISTIC REGISTRATION OF PERSONS

Theoretically, forensic registration (and identification) falls under the domain of criminalistic techniques (forensics). Specifically, the criminalist Jovanović states: “Criminalistic registration is a branch of criminalistic techniques that focuses on finding and refining the most suitable scientific-technical methods for registering persons, with the aim of their subsequent identification and the resolution of criminal cases” (Jovanović, 1981, p. 19).

This implies that registration should be understood as a step toward achieving the goal of an investigation, which is the identification of the perpetrator of a criminal act. It is generally known that forensics, as a science, applies discoveries from other sciences (natural or technical) to achieve its objectives. Throughout history, the scientific works of renowned scientists (biologists, anthropologists, etc.), particularly those related to human biometric characteristics, have immediately found application in forensics and, consequently, in our area of interest — forensic registration.

The renowned French criminalist Alphonse Bertillon (1853–1914), who worked for many years in the French police, made the first pioneering attempts to establish a system for registering persons based on scientific principles. According to Jovanović, it is worth noting that methods for registering offenders existed prior to this, but these were often brutal, primarily consisting of mutilation and branding. Bertillon based his registration system on the following assumptions: (Jovanović, 1981, p. 21)

- The human skeleton ceases to develop after the age of twenty, and its structure remains unchanged;
- Each person possesses strictly individual skeletal measurements, meaning no two individuals in the world have entirely identical skeletons; and
- By measuring specific parts of the body, a previously registered person can later be reliably identified.

Bertillon’s method, known as “Bertillonage”, was adopted in forensic work, particularly in the Paris police prefecture. Bertillon conducted measurements of various parts of the human body: arm length, head width, height, etc. These data were recorded on cards, which were later classified based on various criteria (age, gender, etc.). It was later scientifically proven that the basis of this system was flawed, as the human skeleton undergoes changes even after the age of twenty, creating room for the revision of this registration method. Nevertheless, the significance of Bertillonage is considerable, as it was the first attempt at forensic registration based on systematic scientific principles. In modern registration practices, the use of photography in three positions (mugshot photography), which Bertillon was the first to implement, is still employed. As a point of interest, it is worth mentioning that in our country, within the Forensic department unit in Bitola, a registration chair from Bertillon’s era is still in existence and use.

During his lifetime, Bertillon staunchly adhered to his method of work and was an opponent of introducing other registration methods. However, discoveries made in the field of individualizing human fingerprints began to find their place in forensic registration. Historically, the individual characteristics of the skin on human fingers were known to people as early as antiquity. However, a somewhat scientific approach to this field can be attributed to the publication of the works of the Italian anatomist Marcello Malpighi, who was the first to attempt to explain the concept of “papillae”. In this context, we would like

to highlight the definition provided in the Guidelines (Article 2): “Papillary lines are ridges on the surface layer of the skin present on the phalanges of the fingers (upper and lower parts for the thumb, and upper, middle, and lower parts for the other fingers), palms, toes, and soles of the feet”.

Many scientists have contributed to the study of fingerprints, and the works of Purkinje and William Herschel are worth mentioning. However, the pioneering step in this field was taken by Sir Francis Galton, who viewed fingerprints through the lens of their identification value. It is also essential to mention Juan Vucetich, who developed a system for classifying papillary lines and introduced this system into the operations of the police department in Buenos Aires, Argentina. Gradually, this method, known as dactyloscopy, began to be applied in countries worldwide. The work with fingerprints is based on four scientifically verified and proven postulates:

- **Immutability** – The patterns of papillary lines are formed in the womb and remain unchanged throughout a person’s life;
- **Individuality** – The patterns of papillary lines on each finger have specific individual characteristics, and no two people in the world have identical fingerprints;
- **Classifiability** – Papillary line patterns can be grouped into several types and
- **Transferability** – Due to the anatomical characteristics of the skin, upon contact with an object, papillary line patterns can be transferred or imprinted onto that object.

Dactyloscopic data, or fingerprints, are studied by a specific branch of forensics known as dactyloscopy. This field is further divided into several subcategories: cheiroscope (the study of papillary lines on the palms), pedoscope (the study of papillary lines on the soles of the feet), and poroscope (the study of the pores of papillary lines).

In our forensic practice, during the registration of persons, the traditional ink method for taking fingerprints is still used. According to the Guidelines, this method involves rolling each finger of both hands, from the right thumb to the left little finger, covering the entire lower phalanx and part of the middle phalanx of the fingers (or the entire lower phalanx and part of the upper phalanx for the thumbs), onto a surface coated with a thin layer of dactyloscopic ink. In addition to the ten fingers, impressions are also taken of the entire palm and the lateral “writing” side of the palm.

All measures in the fingerprint collection process are carried out by a trained professional – a forensic technician. The ink method requires the use of appropriate equipment, which includes: (Maksimović, 2000, p. 97)

- Special dactyloscopic ink;
- Flat plates, typically made of glass or metal;
- A rubber roller;
- Paper forms for dactyloscopy and
- Cleaning parts for the hands after fingerprinting.

Based on field experience, we would like to highlight several situations that may arise during the process. Specifically, care must be taken to ensure that the person’s hands are clean and free of any contaminants. A common mistake is the mixing up of hands,

meaning that fingerprints from the right hand are mistakenly rolled onto the section of the card designated for the left hand.

All fingerprints are taken on appropriate forms, specifically dactyloscopic cards, which are later sent to the Department for Forensic Examinations (hereinafter, DFE), where the fingerprints are stored in the records.

The introduction of the new ABIS system brings several changes regarding dactyloscopy, including the digital collection of fingerprints via LiveScan and a reduction in the documentation associated with the ink method. This undoubtedly improves the quality of the fingerprints themselves and enables their immediate network-based retrieval. The second change pertains to the collection of fingerprints from the fingertips. Currently, the ABIS system does not offer the option to collect these digitally via LiveScan; instead, they must be taken on paper and subsequently scanned into the system. This approach expands the database and increases the likelihood of positive identification by matching stored papillary line traces from unknown perpetrators.

The second part of registration, as mentioned earlier, involves photography, specifically mugshot photography introduced by Alphonse Bertillon. This consists of photographing the registered person in three positions:

- Frontal (en face) – the face is photographed from the front;
- Right profile and
- Left semi-profile.

The purpose of these three positions is to capture the appearance of the face, adhering to several rules. In the frontal photograph, the face must not have any aids or accessories. Such items should be visible in the left semi-profile photograph. Additionally, the right-profile photograph must include the name of the organizational unit where the person is registered and display the corresponding dactyloscopic number. Registration photographs are, by rule, scaled photographs produced at a 1:10 ratio to allow for the calculation of dimensions of specific facial features.

The aspect of calculating facial dimensions is retained in the ABIS system's photography process. The software itself offers the capability to biometrically process the photograph and compare it with unknown individuals. It must be noted that, at the time of writing, this feature is still in an experimental phase, and we do not have data on its successful functionality.

The third part, the collection of reference biological material, pertains to obtaining material that can later be used for DNA analysis. According to Article 2 of the Guidelines, any biological material of human origin (blood, tissue, hair, and other bodily fluids) is considered a sample for DNA analysis. In practice, during the registration of a person, the reference (undisputed) biological material is collected by taking a swab from the oral cavity using specialized forensic collectors. If it is not possible to obtain an oral swab from the individual, the biological material may be collected in another form (e.g., blood or hair). Obtaining a DNA profile is of significant forensic importance, as it provides the opportunity to conduct DNA analysis with biological traces found at the crime scene for which no identification has yet been established.

To conclude this section, we would like to highlight two practical situations that arise during the registration of persons. First, it is increasingly common in practice for individuals to refuse to undergo registration. The reasons for this can vary widely, including distrust of the police, fear of potential misuse of the material, and so forth. In

such cases, the Public prosecutor, upon the request of the police, issues an order mandating the individual to cooperate with the police. This prolongs the procedure, and there are frequent instances where, even with an issued order, individuals continue to refuse registration.

The second observation, based on our experience, is one we believe would be beneficial to include in the official materials (forms) used during registration. It is well-known that identical twins share the same DNA structure. Therefore, we propose that during the forensic registration process, there should be a form indicating whether the individual has an identical twin. This would provide valuable information that could be useful in the subsequent identification process.

2. FORENSIC IDENTIFICATION OF PERSONS

The processes of forensic registration and identification are closely interconnected. However, the identification method can also stand alone. In practice, it is possible to identify persons or objects that are not previously registered in the databases of investigative authorities. In such cases, this is referred to as direct identification. Here, identification is conducted by comparing a found trace (e.g., a fingerprint) with a sample taken from an individual at the time, for whom no prior data exists in the databases of registered persons. The other type, indirect identification (which is more commonly used in practice), involves the identification of characteristics (papillary lines, DNA samples) previously collected by investigative authorities through the forensic registration process and stored in various databases, such as dactyloscopic collections.

It is important to note that identification, in a general sense, is a procedure used to establish the sameness or similarity between two “objects” and is applied in various natural sciences, each with its own specific methods of proof. In criminalistics, or more precisely in forensics, the subjects of identification may include persons, remains, or objects. In the first two cases, these are human beings who possess unique characteristics that distinguish each individual from all others. The discovery of the uniqueness of these characteristics is a process that has spanned centuries in science, with many scientists contributing to it. We believe this process is not fully complete even today and that, in addition to the existing characteristics used, there is room for the discovery and introduction of new ones. Terminologically, these characteristics (in humans) that enable identification are referred to as identification markers. In forensics, three types of identification markers are used to establish a person’s identity: (Maksimović, 2000, p. 77)

- **Legal markers:** Characteristics acquired by an individual based on existing legal regulations, such as personal name, citizenship, etc.
- **Factual markers:** Characteristics acquired by an individual at birth (or death), such as date and place of birth.
- **Physical markers:** Characteristics related to gender, physical appearance, the pattern of papillary lines, etc.

Methodologically, the primary approach in identification is the process of comparison, and it can be concluded that identification involves comparing these three types of markers to establish their authenticity. This means that forensic identification is the process of verifying the authenticity of a person’s legal, factual, and physical markers.

The focus of our paper is so-called indirect identification, which is based on markers previously collected in specialized registration databases and does not require the physical presence of the identification subject during the process. According to the author Maksimović, this type of identification can be divided into three subgroups: (Maksimović, 2000, p. 82)

- Identification based on personal description, photograph, or photo-robot;
- Identification based on papillary lines and
- Identification based on DNA samples.

We will attempt to briefly explain each subgroup individually, as this classification is also adhered to in our Guidelines.

The first group, identification based on personal appearance/description, is the least reliable type of identification due to potential changes in physical appearance. Nevertheless, it remains one of the most commonly used methods in forensic fieldwork, particularly in recent years, primarily due to the increased presence of surveillance cameras in facilities where criminal acts occur. It is rare to find a company or commercial space without surveillance cameras, and there is a growing trend of installing such cameras in private homes as well. For these reasons, identifying or recognizing a potential perpetrator based on their physical appearance has become a daily practice in forensic work.

Individual physical markers, such as scars, moles, tattoos, and similar features, can play a significant role in this type of identification. Therefore, it is crucial to record these markers during the registration process.

In our opinion, this subgroup of identification also includes identification based on forensic (mugshot) photography. Photography is important because it captures the physical appearance of the individual, particularly details such as hair and eye colour. In practice, photographs of specific dimensions are used, and a recent development in this area is the introduction of digital photography with the ABIS system. Digital photography enables biometric comparison of an individual's physical appearance with footage of unknown perpetrators stored in the Department for Forensic Examinations (DFI).

The second subgroup, identification based on papillary lines, is also known in the literature as papillary identification. The core of this identification lies in detecting the ridges on the skin, known as papillae, and their arrangement. Papillae are most densely distributed on the fingers, palms, and soles. Papillary lines form so-called "papillary line patterns", which have been proven to be unique for each finger of every human being, even differing between identical twins. Research by scientists in this field has confirmed the four premises about papillary lines mentioned earlier (immutability, individuality, classifiability, and transferability). The methodology used for the identification of papillary lines in the Republic of North Macedonia is the so-called ACE-V methodology, an acronym for Analysis, Comparison, Evaluation, and Verification. These are the four phases that every papillary line trace undergoes in the OFI laboratories.

Fingerprints from registered individuals are directly entered into the databases. The shortcomings of the previous model, as identified by Божинов (2019), highlight several methodological limitations, first with the previous ink-based fingerprinting method, it was necessary to first digitize the prints from the cards before entering them into the AFIS (Automated Fingerprint Identification System). By entering fingerprints into the databases, it becomes possible to compare them with papillary line traces found during a

crime scene investigation, enabling positive identification. For positive identification between two papillary line samples, the OFI uses a numerical method that involves matching 12 characteristics between the samples.

The introduction of the ABIS system will streamline the identification process, primarily because fingerprints will be collected using a LiveScan scanner during registration and immediately converted into digital form. This allows them to be instantly entered into the databases of registered persons, enabling the system to check whether an individual with such fingerprints already exists in the database. Consequently, this will shorten the procedure and significantly reduce the use of paper (or paperwork).

The final subgroup for identification is identification based on DNA material. This is the most recent method of identification, with its application beginning in the late 1980s in the United Kingdom and the United States. According to the Guidelines, the term DNA is defined broadly as: “genetic material specific to each human individual and the carrier of heredity”.

As noted in recent research (Коцевска, 2018): “Every individual inherits genetic material from their parents. During the fertilization process, the egg and sperm combine to create a new individual. This new individual has two copies of genetic material — one from the mother and one from the father”.

A detailed and authoritative exposition of the structure of the DNA molecule is presented by the author Данилова (Данилова, 2017). She says that – “An exception in DNA identification exists with identical twins, who share the same DNA structure. DNA molecules are present in every cell of the human body. The structure of DNA consists of two parallel strands or helices containing three groups of atoms: sugars, phosphorus, and nitrogen. Nitrogen binds to sugar, and four nitrogenous bases are distinguished: adenine (A), thymine (T), cytosine (C), and guanine (G). The entire process of DNA identification is based on the combinations formed by these four nitrogenous bases in the DNA sequence. Specifically, the order in which the nitrogenous bases alternate in the sequence is unique to each human individual, except in the case of identical twins”.

Simply put, to identify an individual, it is necessary to observe a specific number of base sequences that repeat along the DNA strand.

We believe it is useful to note that DNA analysis is performed on samples of biological origin (blood, tissue, saliva, hair, and other bodily fluids). The repetitions of these sequences are then subjected to statistical interpretation, which expresses the probability of such repetition occurring in the entire population.

Regarding DNA identification, the Department for Forensic Examinations (DFE) follows the recommendations of ENFSI (European Network of Forensic Science Institutes), which are incorporated into the legal text of the Guidelines. In this regard, specialized collectors meeting the latest standards in the field have been introduced for use during fieldwork registration.

To conclude the section on DNA identification, we would like to elaborate on a procedure that was in place at DFE until 2012. Specifically, if a positive identification was made based on biological material (DNA analysis), the identity of the identified person was determined solely based on the data provided by the organizational unit that submitted the material. This approach left room for numerous errors, as the registered individual could intentionally (or unintentionally) provide incorrect information about themselves. This practice was changed with the introduction of the Guidelines for Registration of Persons in 2014, which introduced the Identity Verification Form. This form provided an option for collecting two fingerprints (left and right index fingers), and if the individual did

not possess identification documents, it was mandatory to submit an extract from the birth registry along with the registration material sent to DFE.

The introduction of this form also changed the way identity verification was conducted between departments within DFE. Specifically, the identity of a person positively identified through DNA analysis undergoes a phase of so-called “cross” identification, where a comparative analysis is performed between the fingerprints submitted on the relevant form for identity verification and the individual’s dactyloscopic card. Essentially, this involves verifying the registration data held by the Dactyloscopy Department and the DNA Analysis Department. If there is any discrepancy in the data, a comparison is made with the data collected during the procedure for obtaining personal (biometric) documents, i.e., the IMAGO system.

It is worth noting that this working model has been retained in the new Guidelines for Registration from January 2024. With this model, DFE eliminates the possibility of errors in identity verification, making it one of the leading forensic institutes in this part of Europe in this field.

CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have attempted to theoretically elaborate on the processes of forensic registration and identification and to highlight the challenges encountered during their implementation in forensic fieldwork in our country. The importance of this aspect of forensics is immense, as failure to establish the identity of a suspect could lead to significant oversights in an investigation, potentially altering its course and resulting in the most undesirable outcome — such as an innocent person being imprisoned.

Our focus was directed toward two processes that began implementation this year: the newly adopted Guidelines and the introduction of the ABIS system into the forensic practices of the organizational units for criminalistic techniques in the country, as well as in the DFE.

The legal provisions related to this issue must be clear and unambiguous. In this regard, our aim was to terminologically clarify the concepts contained in the Guidelines and to point out shortcomings. In particular, we believe that further attention should be given to the increasing number of individuals who refuse to provide their personal information for registration during the process.

The challenges of implementing the ABIS system are significant. This entails replacing the previous ink-based dactyloscopy method with a new, so-called digital fingerprint, which undoubtedly represents a step forward in our forensic practice. However, we would like to emphasize that for the quality implementation of such a step, a longer testing period is necessary. We believe that the more thorough the system testing, the less room there will be for errors once the system becomes fully operational.

In conclusion, we would like to state that these two processes are part of the Ministry of Internal Affairs’ efforts to introduce operational standards that align with those of European countries (police forces) in this field.

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